

Age-Based Variation In Phonological Lenition: An Acoustic Study Of Consonant Substitution And Omission In Dhani Punjabi

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Abstract: *This acoustic study investigates age-based variation in phonological lenition processes within the Dhani dialect of Punjabi, spoken in Kala Gujran, Jhelum, Pakistan. Focusing on three phonological processes (1) substitution of voiceless aspirated velar plosive /k^h/ with voiceless glottal fricative /h/, (2) substitution of voiced velar plosive /g/ with voiced velar fricative /ɣ/, and (3) omission of voiceless glottal fricative /h/ in word-medial position the study examines how these processes differ across two age groups (20–35 years and 35–50 years). Data were collected from twelve native speakers (six per age group, equally divided by gender) using connected speech passages. Acoustic analysis using Praat software revealed significant age-based differences in the substitution of /k^h/ with /h/, with younger speakers exhibiting notably higher rates (86.7–94.7%) compared to older speakers (62.3–72.3%), suggesting ongoing sound change. In contrast, substitution of /g/ with /ɣ/ and omission of /h/ were near-categorical across both age groups (91.6–99.2% and 98.2–100%, respectively), indicating stable phonological rules. Gender-based differences were observed, with males consistently showing higher rates of lenition than females. The findings contribute to understanding apparent-time sound change in under-documented Indo-Aryan dialects and highlight the complex interplay between articulatory economy, phonological conditioning, and sociolinguistic factors in shaping variation patterns.*

Keywords: Phonological lenition, age-based variation, Dhani dialect, Punjabi, acoustic analysis, sound change

Introduction

The study of language variation and change has long recognized age as a critical factor in understanding phonological processes (Labov, 1994, 2001; Chambers, 2003). Age-graded variation systematic differences in linguistic behavior across age cohorts can provide crucial insights into whether observed patterns represent stable sociolinguistic stratification or ongoing sound change in progress. In the apparent-time framework, differences between younger and older speakers are interpreted as evidence of language change, assuming that speakers' linguistic systems remain relatively stable after adolescence (Bailey et al., 1991; Tagliamonte, 2006). This methodological approach has proven particularly valuable for studying sound changes in progress, as it allows researchers to infer diachronic patterns from synchronic data without the necessity of long-term longitudinal studies (Labov, 1994). When younger speakers exhibit systematically higher frequencies of a particular variant compared to older speakers, this pattern is interpreted as evidence that the variant is increasing in the community, representing an ongoing linguistic change. Conversely, when age differences are minimal or absent, the feature may be considered stable across generations (Chambers, 2003; Tagliamonte, 2012). Within the broader context of Indo-Aryan languages, Punjabi exhibits rich dialectal diversity that remains largely under-documented from an acoustic perspective. Punjabi, spoken by approximately 80 million people

in Pakistan and another 30 million in India, constitutes one of the world's most widely spoken languages (Simons & Fennig, 2018). Despite its demographic significance, systematic acoustic documentation of its dialectal variation remains surprisingly limited. Among its numerous varieties, the Dhani dialect spoken primarily in the Pothohar Plateau region, including parts of Rawalpindi Division, Chakwal, and southern Jhelum and Attock districts represents a particularly under-researched variety. According to Grierson's Linguistic Survey of India (1917), Dhani belongs to the Northern cluster of Lahnda (Western Punjabi), occupying a transitional position between the more conservative Pothohari dialects and the innovative southern varieties. This geographical and linguistic positioning makes Dhani particularly valuable for understanding the historical development and ongoing changes within the Punjabi dialect continuum. While descriptive accounts (Grierson, 1917) and preliminary studies on loanword adaptation (Hasan & Khan, 2019) exist, systematic acoustic investigation of Dhani phonological processes, particularly those involving lenition, remains absent from the literature. This absence is particularly significant given that Dhani speakers themselves report perceptions of their dialect as distinct from neighboring varieties, with phonological features often cited as the primary markers of this distinctiveness (personal observation, community discussions).

Lenition the weakening of consonants constitutes one of the most extensively documented phonological processes across world languages (Lavoie, 2001; Kirchner, 2001; Bauer, 2008). This process typically involves shifts from stops to fricatives (spirantization), from fricatives to approximants, or complete deletion, and is often conditioned by prosodic position and phonological context. The phonetic motivation for lenition lies in articulatory economy: speakers tend to reduce articulatory effort in contexts where perceptual distinctiveness is less critical, such as in intervocalic positions, unstressed syllables, and casual speech styles (Ohala, 1983; Kingston, 2008). The cross-linguistic prevalence of lenition patterns from the intervocalic voicing and spirantization in Spanish (Hualde, 2005) to the debuccalization of stops in varieties of English (Docherty & Foulkes, 1999) suggests universal phonetic tendencies, though the specific implementation of these tendencies varies across languages and dialects (Kirchner, 2001). In South Asian languages, lenition patterns affecting velar and glottal consonants have been observed in various varieties (Baart, 2003; Hussain, 2004; Malik & Kokub, 2020), yet the extent to which these processes exhibit age-based variation remains unexplored for many dialects, including Dhani. The theoretical significance of examining age-based variation in lenition lies in its potential to reveal the time-depth and social embedding of these processes: categorical lenition across all age groups suggests a long-established rule, while age-graded variation indicates ongoing change (Labov, 2001). The present study addresses this gap by examining three lenition processes in Dhani Punjabi through an apparent-time framework: (1) substitution of voiceless aspirated velar plosive /k^h/ with voiceless glottal fricative /h/, (2) substitution of voiced velar plosive /g/ with voiced velar fricative /ɣ/, and (3) omission of voiceless glottal fricative /h/ in word-medial position. These three processes were selected based on preliminary naturalistic observations in the Kala Gujran community, where they were observed to occur frequently in casual speech. The selection allows for comparison across different types of lenition: the first involves both place and manner change (velar stop to glottal fricative), the second involves manner change only (stop to fricative with same place of articulation), and the third involves complete deletion. By comparing acoustic data from younger (20–35 years) and older (35–50 years) speakers, this study aims to determine whether these processes represent stable features of Dhani phonology or reflect ongoing sound change. The choice of age groups follows established sociolinguistic practice, capturing speakers before and after the critical period for language stabilization while avoiding the extremes of adolescence (where speech is most variable) and advanced age (where physiological changes may affect production) (Labov, 2001; Tagliamonte, 2006).

Additionally, the investigation examines gender-based differences in lenition rates, given the well-documented tendency for women to favor more standard or conservative variants (Labov, 2001;

Meyerhoff, 2018). The relationship between gender and linguistic variation has been extensively studied across diverse speech communities, with findings consistently showing that women tend to use forms closer to the standard or prestige norm, while men lead in the use of vernacular and innovative variants (Eckert, 1989; Milroy, 1987). This pattern has been attributed to women's greater sensitivity to overt prestige norms, their role as primary socializers of children, and the differential social pressures faced by men and women in community networks (Labov, 2001). The present study tests whether these general patterns hold in the Dhani speech community, examining whether women show lower rates of lenition (more conservative speech) compared to men, and whether any gender differences interact with age-based variation. The significance of this study extends beyond the documentation of a single dialect. First, it contributes to the broader understanding of sound change in progress within Indo-Aryan languages, an area that remains under-investigated compared to Germanic and Romance languages (Hock, 1991). Second, by comparing three distinct lenition processes within the same speech community, the study can reveal whether different phonological processes follow different trajectories of change a finding with implications for theories of phonological change (Kiparsky, 1995; Blevins, 2004). Third, the acoustic methodology employed provides objective, replicable evidence that can serve as a baseline for future studies of sound change in the region. Fourth, the documentation of Dhani contributes to the preservation of Pakistan's linguistic heritage, responding to calls for increased attention to under-documented language varieties (Sugono, 2008; Austin & Sallabank, 2011). Finally, the findings may have practical applications for language teaching and speech technology development for Punjabi varieties, which currently lack resources informed by dialectal variation. In the following sections, the paper presents a detailed review of relevant literature on lenition and age-based variation, followed by the methodology employed, the results of the acoustic analysis, a discussion of findings in relation to theoretical frameworks, and concluding implications for the study of phonological variation and change.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 Lenition and Spirantization

Lenition, broadly defined as consonant weakening, encompasses a range of phonetic and phonological processes that reduce the articulatory effort required for consonant production. These processes include spirantization (transformation of stops into fricatives), debuccalization (reduction to glottal stop or /h/), degemination (shortening of geminate consonants), and complete deletion (Lavoie, 2001; Bauer, 2008). Lenition is often conceptualized as occurring along a hierarchical scale of decreasing articulatory effort: voiceless stop > voiced stop > voiceless fricative > voiced fricative > approximant > deletion (Lass, 1984; Hock, 1991). While this scale captures the directional tendencies of lenition processes, the specific pathways of weakening vary across languages and phonological contexts (Kirchner, 2001).

Kirchner (2001) proposed an influential effort-based approach to lenition, grounded in principles of articulatory phonology (Browman & Goldstein, 1989). According to this framework, speakers continuously minimize articulatory effort while maintaining sufficient perceptual distinctiveness to ensure successful communication. Lenition occurs when the perceptual benefits of a full articulation are outweighed by the articulatory costs, leading speakers to reduce the magnitude or duration of constriction gestures. Within this framework, the susceptibility of specific consonants to lenition is determined by their articulatory complexity: sounds requiring precise constriction, complex coordination, or maintenance of voicing during closure are most vulnerable to weakening (Kirchner, 2001; Lavoie, 2001).

Voiced stops, particularly those in intervocalic positions, are especially susceptible to lenition because maintaining voicing throughout oral closure requires complex articulatory coordination (Ohala, 1983; Kingston, 2008). During stop closure, intraoral pressure rises rapidly; to maintain voicing, the vocal folds must continue vibrating against this increasing pressure, a process that requires precise adjustment

of transglottal pressure differences. By reducing the degree of constriction to produce a fricative or approximant, speakers can sustain voicing more easily while reducing overall articulatory effort (Westbury & Keating, 1986). This phonetic motivation explains the cross-linguistic prevalence of intervocalic voicing and spirantization, from the well-known patterns in Spanish (Hualde, 2005) to similar processes in Celtic (Ó Dochartaigh, 1980) and many other language families.

Spirantization specifically refers to the transformation of plosives into fricatives (Giannakis, 2013). This process represents a partial reduction in constriction degree: stops involve complete closure of the vocal tract, while fricatives involve a narrow constriction that allows continuous airflow. For voiced velar stops, spirantization yields the voiced velar fricative /ɣ/. Cross-linguistic evidence demonstrates that /g/ lenition is favored in specific phonological contexts: intervocalic position (between vowels), post-vocalic position (after vowels before consonants), and unstressed syllables (Lavoie, 2001). The conditioning role of vowel context is particularly significant; high vowels /i/ and /u/ have been shown to promote spirantization of velar stops due to the articulatory compatibility between the fronted or backed tongue position for the vowel and the velar place of articulation (Ortega-Llebaria, 2003; Recasens & Espinosa, 2009).

The glottal fricative /h/ occupies a unique position within consonant inventories, distinguished by its lack of supraglottal constriction. Unlike other fricatives, which involve active constriction at specific places of articulation (labiodental, dental, alveolar, palatal, velar), /h/ is produced solely through glottal friction with the vocal folds partially open and no obstruction in the oral cavity (Ladefoged & Maddieson, 1996). This articulatory configuration results in acoustic characteristics that are fundamentally different from other consonants: /h/ has no fixed formant structure, its spectral shape is determined by the surrounding vowels, and it lacks the robust noise bursts or formant transitions that characterize other consonants (Stevens, 1998). This articulatory and acoustic weakness renders /h/ highly susceptible to deletion in connected speech, particularly in post-vocalic positions where it is surrounded by more acoustically salient segments (Pierrehumbert, 2003; Ohala, 2014). The deletion of /h/ represents the endpoint of a lenition continuum: from a fully articulated glottal fricative, to a breathy voice quality on adjacent vowels, to complete absence (Pierrehumbert & Talkin, 1992).

2.2 Age-Based Variation and Sound Change

The apparent-time construct constitutes one of the foundational methodologies in variationist sociolinguistics, allowing researchers to infer diachronic language change from synchronic data (Labov, 1994; Bailey et al., 1991). This approach assumes that linguistic changes in progress can be observed by comparing speakers of different ages at a single point in time, under the premise that individual speakers' linguistic systems remain relatively stable after adolescence (Tagliamonte, 2006). If younger speakers exhibit higher frequencies of a particular variant than older speakers, this pattern is interpreted as evidence of ongoing change, with the younger generation advancing the innovative variant (Labov, 2001). Conversely, if all age groups show similar frequencies, the feature is considered stable across generations, though it may still be subject to style-shifting and social stratification (Chambers, 2003).

The apparent-time framework has been validated through real-time studies that track the same speakers over decades, confirming that age differences in synchronic data often correspond to actual historical changes (Labov, 1994; Trudgill, 1988). However, researchers must distinguish between true generational change and age-graded variation patterns where speakers use different variants at different stages of life but the community overall does not change (Chambers, 2003). For example, adolescents may use innovative variants that they later abandon as adults, creating apparent-time differences that do not represent long-term change. Distinguishing between these possibilities requires examining the trajectory of change across multiple age groups and considering social factors such as class, gender,

and community norms (Tagliamonte, 2012).

Research across numerous speech communities has established that younger speakers often lead in the adoption of lenited, reduced variants (Labov, 2001; Mesthrie et al., 2009). This pattern has been attributed to several converging factors. First, younger speakers typically engage in more informal speech styles and are more influenced by peer-group interactions where speech economy the tendency to minimize articulatory effort is prioritized over careful articulation (Hock, 1991). Second, increased exposure to casual speech styles through media, digital communication, and social networks may accelerate the adoption of reduced variants among younger generations (Tagliamonte, 2012). Third, younger speakers may be less subject to normative pressure against innovation, as the standardizing institutions (schools, religious institutions, traditional media) exert less influence on their linguistic behavior (Milroy & Milroy, 1985). Fourth, in situations of dialect contact or language shift, younger speakers are often at the forefront of linguistic change (Britain, 2002).

The rate and direction of sound change are influenced by a complex interaction of internal linguistic factors and external social factors. Internally, changes typically begin in phonetically favorable contexts (e.g., intervocalic position for lenition) and gradually extend to other contexts (Labov, 1994). Externally, changes may be led by particular social groups often younger speakers, men, or those at the center of dense social networks and may carry social meanings that influence their adoption or rejection (Eckert, 2000). The study of age-based variation in lenition therefore provides insight not only into the trajectory of sound change but also into the social embedding of phonological processes.

2.3 Gender and Phonological Variation

Gender-based differences in phonological variation have been extensively documented across diverse speech communities, emerging as one of the most consistent findings in variationist sociolinguistics (Labov, 2001; Meyerhoff, 2018). The general pattern is remarkably stable: women tend to favor standard or conservative variants more than men, while men lead in the use of vernacular and innovative forms (Eckert, 1989; Milroy, 1987). This pattern has been observed in numerous languages and communities, from the classic studies of New York City English (Labov, 1966) to contemporary investigations of global Englishes (Meyerhoff, 2018).

Several explanations have been proposed for this consistent gender difference. The prestige-based explanation suggests that women are more sensitive to overt prestige norms because their social status is more closely tied to linguistic behavior (Labov, 2001). In many societies, women's social networks are more oriented toward institutional norms (schools, workplaces), while men's networks are more locally focused, reinforcing vernacular norms (Milroy, 1987). The social network explanation emphasizes differences in the structure of men's and women's social networks: women's networks are often more dense and multiplex, potentially reinforcing community norms, while men's networks may be more loosely structured, allowing for greater innovation (Milroy & Milroy, 1992). The identity-based explanation focuses on the symbolic meanings associated with variants: men may adopt vernacular forms to index masculinity, toughness, or local authenticity, while women may avoid these forms to distance themselves from such associations (Eckert, 2000).

Recent research has complicated the picture, demonstrating that gender interacts with other social factors such as age, class, ethnicity, and community type (Meyerhoff, 2018). The gender pattern is strongest in stable, stratified communities and may be attenuated or reversed in communities undergoing rapid social change or where women are at the forefront of change from above (Labov, 2001). Moreover, the relationship between gender and language is not binary: research increasingly recognizes the importance of examining gender as a social practice rather than a fixed category (Eckert & McConnell-Ginet, 1992). Nevertheless, the consistent finding of gender differentiation in phonological variation across diverse contexts supports the inclusion of gender as a crucial variable in studies of sound change, including the investigation of lenition processes in Dhani Punjabi.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Participants

This study employed a qualitative experimental research design, utilizing non-probability purposive sampling to investigate age-based variation in phonological lenition processes within the Dhani dialect. Twelve native speakers of the Dhani dialect from Kala Gujran, a village in District Jhelum, Punjab, Pakistan, participated in the study. The selection of Kala Gujran ensured a homogeneous speech community with strong linguistic traditions relatively insulated from urban linguistic influences.

Participants were divided into two age groups following the apparent-time framework. Group 1 comprised six participants aged 20–35 years (3 males, 3 females), representing younger adult speakers who may be more susceptible to ongoing sound changes. Group 2 comprised six participants aged 35–50 years (3 males, 3 females), representing older speakers whose phonological patterns reflect more conservative norms. All participants met stringent selection criteria: they were born and raised in Kala Gujran, had resided continuously in the region, used Dhani as their primary language, and demonstrated normal hearing and speech abilities. Crucially, participants were not informed of the specific research objectives to minimize observer effects (Labov, 1972).

3.2 Stimuli and Data Collection

Three connected paragraphs were developed containing target words exhibiting the three phonological processes under investigation. Target words were identified through preliminary naturalistic observation in community settings—including family gatherings, marketplace interactions, and informal social events—without disclosing the research purpose. This approach ensured that target words represented genuine dialect features rather than researcher-imposed artifacts. Each paragraph contained multiple tokens of each target sound type distributed across different positions within phrases and sentences to minimize participant awareness. Paragraphs were written in Shahmukhi script and participants engaged in practice sessions to ensure familiarity.

Recordings were conducted in quiet environments using a high-quality external microphone positioned approximately seven to eight inches from participants' mouths. All recordings were captured directly into Praat software (Boersma & Weenink, 2023) at a sampling rate of 44,100 Hz with 16-bit quantization, ensuring sufficient frequency range and amplitude resolution. Each participant read all three paragraphs three times, providing three recording iterations per participant to enable assessment of within-speaker consistency. Recordings were saved as uncompressed WAV files for subsequent analysis. Ethical protocols were followed, with participants providing informed consent and assurance of confidentiality.

3.3 Acoustic Analysis

Acoustic analysis was conducted using Praat software, examining waveforms and spectrograms for each target segment with systematic procedures to identify the three phonological processes. For the analysis of /k^h/ substitution by /h/, three acoustic features were examined: presence or absence of stop closure (indicated by near-zero amplitude in waveform and dark band in spectrogram), presence or absence of burst release (sharp spike in waveform and high-frequency energy concentration), and presence of glottal frication (diffuse, low-amplitude aperiodic noise across frequency spectrum). Substitution was confirmed when closure and burst were absent and glottal frication was present (Stevens, 1998).

For the analysis of /g/ substitution by /ɣ/, analysis focused on closure duration, voicing patterns, and

frication characteristics. Voiced stop production is characterized by closure interval with potential voicing bar, followed by release burst and formant transitions. Voiced fricative /ɣ/ exhibits continuous voicing with no closure phase, accompanied by turbulent airflow as low-to-mid frequency aperiodic energy (Ladefoged & Johnson, 2015). Substitution was confirmed when closure and burst were absent with continuous voicing and turbulent noise.

For the analysis of /h/ omission, the primary acoustic indicator was the absence of glottal frication noise where /h/ would be expected. Spectrograms were examined for the characteristic diffuse, high-frequency energy pattern associated with /h/. When such energy was absent and the preceding vowel transitioned smoothly into the following sound without interruption, omission was confirmed (Mahesh, Dutta & Pandey, 2017).

All recordings were analyzed auditorily and visually by the researcher, with decisions cross-checked through repeated listening and spectrographic examination. Results were tabulated by participant, recording iteration, and target sound type, calculating raw frequencies and percentages for each phonological process across age groups and genders.

4. Results

4.1 Substitution of /k^h/ with /h/

Table 1: Substitution rates for /k^h/ → /h/ across age groups

Group	Recording 1	Recording 2	Recording 3	Mean
F1 (20-35)	86.7%	86.7%	86.7%	86.7%
M1 (20-35)	93.3%	95.4%	95.4%	94.7%
Younger Mean	90.0%	91.1%	91.1%	90.7%
F2 (35-50)	73.3%	73.4%	70.0%	72.3%
M2 (35-50)	66.7%	63.4%	56.7%	62.3%
Older Mean	70.0%	68.4%	63.4%	67.3%

Figure 1: Substitution of /k^h/ with /h/ in the compound word [pəɾea lihea]

The acoustic analysis reveals absence of stop closure and burst release characteristic of plosives, with

continuous low-amplitude frication noise indicating glottal fricative articulation. The age-based difference is striking: younger speakers show consistently higher substitution rates (mean 90.7%) compared to older speakers (mean 67.3%). Within both age groups, males exhibit higher substitution rates than females (94.7% vs. 86.7% in younger group; 62.3% vs. 72.3% in older group).

4.2 Substitution of /g/ with /ɣ/

Table 2: Substitution rates for /g/ → /ɣ/ across age groups

Group	Recording 1	Recording 2	Recording 3	Mean
F1 (20-35)	93.4%	94.7%	93.3%	93.8%
M1 (20-35)	98.7%	98.8%	100%	99.2%
Younger Mean	96.1%	96.8%	96.7%	96.5%
F2 (35-50)	90.7%	92.0%	92.1%	91.6%
M2 (35-50)	90.7%	94.7%	96.0%	93.8%
Older Mean	90.7%	93.4%	94.1%	92.7%

Figure 2: Substitution of /g/ with /ɣ/ in the word [paɣəl]

Spectrographic analysis shows continuous voicing with low to mid-frequency aperiodic energy, absence of closure phase, and turbulent airflow—features characteristic of voiced velar fricative /ɣ/. Unlike the /k^h/ → /h/ substitution, substitution of /g/ → /ɣ/ approaches near-categorical status across both age groups (younger mean 96.5%, older mean 92.7%). The age difference, while present, is considerably smaller (3.8 percentage points) compared to the /k^h/ → /h/ substitution (23.4 percentage points).

4.3 Omission of /h/

Table 3: Omission rates for /h/ in word-medial position across age groups

Group	Recording 1	Recording 2	Recording 3	Mean
F1 (20-35)	100%	97.8%	96.7%	98.2%
M1 (20-35)	100%	100%	100%	100%
Younger Mean	100%	98.9%	98.4%	99.1%
F2 (35-50)	98.9%	98.9%	98.9%	98.9%
M2 (35-50)	100%	100%	100%	100%
Older Mean	99.5%	99.5%	99.5%	99.5%

Figure 3: Omission of /h/ in the phrase [tʃandɛ nɛ]

The absence of aperiodic noise, diffuse high-frequency energy, and the smooth transition from preceding vowel to following consonant confirm the omission of /h/. Omission rates are exceptionally high across both age groups, approaching universality (younger mean 99.1%, older mean 99.5%). Male speakers exhibit 100% omission across both age groups, while females show marginally lower rates (98.2% for younger females, 98.9% for older females).

5. Discussion

5.1 Age-Based Variation in Lenition Patterns

The findings reveal striking differences in age-based variation across the three phonological processes examined. The substitution of /k^h/ with /h/ exhibits a robust age difference: younger speakers show substitution rates nearly 24 percentage points higher than older speakers (90.7% vs. 67.3%). This pattern strongly suggests ongoing sound change in progress, with younger speakers increasingly favoring the lenited, fricative variant over the more articulatorily demanding aspirated stop.

This finding aligns with Lavoie's (2001) theoretical framework, which predicts that lenition processes are favored in casual, rapid speech. Younger speakers, who typically engage in more informal speech styles and are more influenced by peer-group interactions (Mesthrie et al., 2009), show higher rates of

lenition. The role of modern media and digital communication in accelerating the adoption of reduced variants (Tagliamonte, 2012) likely contributes to this pattern.

In contrast, substitution of /g/ with /ɣ/ and omission of /h/ show minimal age differences. The near-categorical status of these processes across both age groups suggests they represent stable, conventionalized features of Dhani phonology rather than ongoing changes. This distinction between processes that are undergoing change and those that have stabilized is theoretically significant, suggesting that different lenition processes operate on different timescales and may be subject to different constraints.

The articulatory motivation for these differences lies in the phonetic properties of the sounds involved. The lenition of /g/ to /ɣ/ and deletion of /h/ are phonetically more natural processes: /g/ lenition reduces the articulatory difficulty of maintaining voicing during closure (Kirchner, 2001), while /h/ deletion exploits the inherent weakness of glottal fricatives (Ladefoged & Maddieson, 1996). These processes may have reached completion earlier in the history of the dialect, resulting in stable, categorical rules. In contrast, the lenition of /k^h/ to /h/ involves a more substantial articulatory shift (from velar to glottal place of articulation) and may represent a more recent innovation.

5.2 Gender-Based Variation

The consistent gender difference observed across all three processes—with males showing higher rates of lenition than females—accords with established sociolinguistic patterns (Labov, 2001; Meyerhoff, 2018). This pattern held across both age groups, suggesting stable gender-based stratification rather than age-graded change. The gender difference was most pronounced for the /k^h/ → /h/ substitution (10 percentage points in the younger group), suggesting that women's preference for more standard variants is particularly strong for processes undergoing change.

These findings contribute to understanding the social embedding of phonological variation in the Dhani speech community. The consistent gender difference suggests that lenited variants carry social meaning, potentially indexing informality, local identity, or masculinity. Women's lower rates of lenition may reflect greater orientation toward prestige norms or more conservative linguistic socialization (Eckert, 1989; Milroy, 1987).

5.3 Phonological Conditioning

The results confirm the role of specific phonological contexts in conditioning lenition. The substitution of /k^h/ with /h/ occurred primarily when the stop was preceded by a vowel, consistent with the cross-linguistic tendency for intervocalic lenition (Lavoie, 2001). The substitution of /g/ with /ɣ/ was particularly frequent after the schwa vowel /ə/, a context where articulatory demands are minimal due to the centralized, weak nature of schwa (Clark, Yallop & Fletcher, 1995).

These conditioning patterns align with theoretical predictions about lenition. Intervocalic position reduces constriction demands and facilitates gestural overlap (Browman & Goldstein, 1989). The particularly high rate of lenition after schwa—a vowel that itself involves reduced articulatory effort—suggests that lenition cascades from vowel to consonant, with reduced vowels facilitating consonant weakening.

5.4 Comparison with Previous Research

The findings extend previous research on lenition in South Asian languages. Baart (2003) documented spirantization of /g/ to /ɣ/ in Saraiki and Hindko dialects, noting its categorical nature in unstressed positions. The present study confirms this pattern for Dhani and provides quantitative acoustic evidence for its near-categorical application. Hussain's (2004) observation of /h/ deletion in Urdu casual speech

is also confirmed for Dhani, with the additional finding that deletion approaches universality in this dialect.

The age-based variation in /k^h/ lenition has not been previously documented for any Punjabi dialect. This finding suggests that this process is currently undergoing change, potentially representing a broader areal tendency in Northwestern Indo-Aryan languages. The direction of change—toward greater lenition—is consistent with cross-linguistic patterns of sound change, where stops frequently weaken to fricatives over time (Hock, 1991).

6. Conclusion

This acoustic study investigated age-based variation in phonological lenition processes in the Dhani dialect of Punjabi. The findings reveal distinct patterns across three processes: (1) substitution of /k^h/ with /h/ shows robust age-based variation, with younger speakers exhibiting significantly higher rates, suggesting ongoing sound change; (2) substitution of /g/ with /ɣ/ is near-categorical across both age groups, indicating a stable phonological rule; and (3) omission of /h/ approaches universality, reflecting the inherent weakness of glottal fricatives. The study contributes to understanding apparent-time sound change in under-documented Indo-Aryan dialects and demonstrates the importance of distinguishing between stable phonological rules and changes in progress. The findings also highlight the complex interplay between articulatory motivation, phonological conditioning, and sociolinguistic factors in shaping variation patterns. Future research should expand the sample size, incorporate additional social variables such as education and media exposure, and examine these processes across a wider range of phonological contexts and speech styles.

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